

Formalizing logical semantics for quantity concepts in geographic information

Eric Top ✉

Utrecht University, Department of Human Geography & Spatial Planning, the Netherlands

Geographic Information (GI) scientists have worked on grounding the theory of their field. However, the conceptualization of quantities is lagging behind. While quantity values are often attributed to spatial regions, the formal assumptions behind these attributions remain opaque to scholars. The aim for my project is to address this problem by developing quantity concepts for GI-related purposes.

In [3] we propose a new definition of extensive and intensive quantities. They are relevant for cartography, because extensive quantities such as population counts are better represented as proportional symbols and intensive quantities such as population densities are more adequately represented as choropleths on cartographic maps, and they are relevant for GI analysis, because these different kinds of quantities permit different operations. Population counts can be meaningfully summed, while population densities can be interpolated, but sums of densities and interpolations of counts are not always valid. In the paper we use quantity domains (e.g., the domain of all subsets of populations and the domain of all population counts) and define extensivity by a correspondence between domains. For example, if two regions are summed, then so are their populations. If the populations are summed, then so are the population counts. That means the measurement relation between them has an extensive property. With population density the same is not true, so this measurement relation does not have that property.

Quantity domains are various and many, and everyone has their own conception of them, yet somehow people manage to align their conceptions. This observation prompted an exploration of *transcepts* [5]. The term transcept is meant to capture that cognitive systems can have different conceptions of the same phenomenon, but still agree that they are addressing the same phenomenon. For example, GI scholars may argue whether a data entry is an object or a field, but they agree that they discuss the same data. Practically, transcepts allow forming views of phenomena by connecting between domains. For example, a population counts and population density may relate back to the same population.

In the theory of quantities the mathematical structure of lattices is important. Lattices are structures with two operators called joins and meets. These operators work according to intuitions usually associated with the words AND and OR. For example, if x and y are true, then also y and x are true. The mathematician Wille [6] introduced a particular kind of lattice called the *concept lattice* and a method of analysis called Formal Concept Analysis (FCA). The lattice is formed through extensions and intensions. Any term has all its examples – its *extension* – and all its characteristics – its *intension*. Formal concept analysts use this notion to infer concepts from graph structures. Here, a concept is a pair of a set of objects and a set of characteristics such that each object has all characteristics. As the terms suggest, extension and intension are related to extensive and intensive quantities. The current working hypothesis in my project is that extension and intension underlie many conceptual intuitions. In [4] we argue that the terms space and place can be understood in terms of extension and intension. It could also be that objects and fields are conceptualized according to these notions. An important aspect of some fields is that they are *homeomerous*: Every part is of the same kind as the whole. Consider for example a land use such as water. If a whole region is water, then also any subregion is water [1, c.f.]. In [2] we define homeomerousness within the framework of FCA. Currently, I am working on a contextualistic

2 Formalizing logical semantics for quantity concepts in geographic information

theory of how FCA can be used for analysing logical implication. The aim is to develop a logical-theoretical grounding of extension and intension and to use this grounding to define concepts and systems of GI.

References

- 1 Giancarlo Guizzardi. On the representation of quantities and their parts in conceptual modeling. In *Formal Ontology in Information Systems*, pages 103–116. IOS Press, 2010.
- 2 Eric Top and Simon Scheider. I am what i have and i have what i am, what am i? In *Formal Ontology in Information Systems*, pages 210–224. IOS Press, 2023.
- 3 Eric Top, Simon Scheider, Haiqi Xu, Enkhbold Nyamsuren, and Niels Steenbergen. The semantics of extensive quantities within geographic information. *Applied Ontology*, 17(3):337–364, 2022.
- 4 Eric J Top, Daniel Romm, and Grant McKenzie. Exploring the Duality of Space and Place through Formal Geo-Concepts. In *Proceedings of the Fourth International Symposium on Platial Information Science (PLATIAL'23)*, Dortmund, Germany, 2023. Zenodo. doi: 10.5281/ZENODO.8286265.
- 5 Eric J Top and Simon Scheider. Transcepts: Connecting entity representations across conceptual views on spatial information (short paper). In *15th International Conference on Spatial Information Theory (COSIT 2022)*. Schloss Dagstuhl-Leibniz-Zentrum für Informatik, 2022.
- 6 Rudolf Wille and Bernhard Ganter. Formal concept analysis, 1996.